

Beyond Looks: A Study on Agent Movement and Audiovisual Spatial Coherence in Augmented Reality

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Statistical Analysis

Valence and Arousal

Boxplot of Valence and Arousal questions 1-2

```
## Using avatar, audio, animation as id variables
```

```
## Warning in geom_signif(inherit.aes = FALSE, data = annotation_df, aes(xmin =  
## start, : Ignoring unknown aesthetics: xmin, xmax, annotations, and y_position
```

```
## Warning in geom_signif(inherit.aes = FALSE, data = annotation_df2, aes(xmin =  
## start, : Ignoring unknown aesthetics: xmin, xmax, annotations, and y_position
```


Animation standing

Audio spatial

Analysis Excitement

descriptive analysis

```
## # A tibble: 12 x 7
##   avatar audio animation variable      n mean  sd
##   <fct> <fct> <fct>   <fct>   <dbl> <dbl> <dbl>
## 1 C     MA     PC     excitement 36 4.25 1.78
## 2 C     MA     PD     excitement 36 4.06 1.79
## 3 C     MA     PS     excitement 36 4.08 1.75
## 4 C     SA     PC     excitement 36 4.28 1.61
## 5 C     SA     PD     excitement 36 4.14 1.82
## 6 C     SA     PS     excitement 36 3.97 1.92
## 7 R     MA     PC     excitement 36 4.75 1.52
## 8 R     MA     PD     excitement 36 4.22 1.97
## 9 R     MA     PS     excitement 36 3.94 1.84
## 10 R    SA     PC     excitement 36 4.28 1.73
## 11 R    SA     PD     excitement 36 4.22 1.71
## 12 R    SA     PS     excitement 36 4.19 1.72
```

mean and SD values grouped by avatar

```
## # A tibble: 2 x 4
##   avatar count mean  sd
##   <fct> <int> <dbl> <dbl>
## 1 C      216 4.13 1.76
## 2 R      216 4.27 1.75
```

mean and SD values grouped by animation

```
## # A tibble: 3 x 4
##   animation count mean  sd
##   <fct>      <int> <dbl> <dbl>
## 1 PC          144 4.39 1.66
## 2 PD          144 4.16 1.81
## 3 PS          144 4.05 1.79
```

mean and SD values grouped by avatar:animation

```
## `summarise()` has grouped output by 'avatar'. You can override using the
## `.groups` argument.
```

```
## # A tibble: 6 x 5
## # Groups:   avatar [2]
##   avatar animation count mean  sd
##   <fct> <fct>      <int> <dbl> <dbl>
## 1 C     PC          72 4.26 1.69
## 2 C     PD          72 4.10 1.79
## 3 C     PS          72 4.03 1.82
## 4 R     PC          72 4.51 1.64
## 5 R     PD          72 4.22 1.83
## 6 R     PS          72 4.07 1.77
```

Outliers

```
## [1] avatar          audio             animation         v_ID
## [5] OrderCondition   Condition        excitement       calmness
## [9] externalization  auvicoherence   auplausibility   distance
## [13] ABP1_BehP1       ABP2_AppP1      ABP3_BehAppMatch ABP4_coherence
```

```
## [17] ABP5_BehExp      ABP6_predict      SP1                SP2
## [21] SP3                 SP4                SP5                avgabp
## [25] avgsp              avgaudio           is.outlier         is.extreme
## <0 Zeilen> (oder row.names mit Länge 0)
```

Normality assumptions (Shapiro-Wilk test and QQ-plot)

```
## # A tibble: 12 x 6
##   avatar audio animation variable  statistic    p
##   <fct> <fct> <fct>   <chr>      <dbl> <dbl>
## 1 C     MA     PC     excitement 0.942 0.0585
## 2 C     MA     PD     excitement 0.946 0.0797
## 3 C     MA     PS     excitement 0.944 0.0654
## 4 C     SA     PC     excitement 0.949 0.0945
## 5 C     SA     PD     excitement 0.935 0.0345
## 6 C     SA     PS     excitement 0.932 0.0281
## 7 R     MA     PC     excitement 0.942 0.0577
## 8 R     MA     PD     excitement 0.922 0.0149
## 9 R     MA     PS     excitement 0.930 0.0254
## 10 R    SA     PC     excitement 0.922 0.0148
## 11 R    SA     PD     excitement 0.944 0.0701
## 12 R    SA     PS     excitement 0.936 0.0393
```


3-way repeated measure Anova

```
## ANOVA Table (type III tests)
##
##           Effect DFn  DFd    F    p p<.05    ges
## 1           avatar 1.00 35.00 1.427 0.240 0.002000
```

```
## 2          audio 1.00 35.00 0.210 0.650      0.000113
## 3          animation 1.43 50.14 2.942 0.078      0.007000
## 4      avatar:audio 1.00 35.00 0.185 0.670      0.000113
## 5      avatar:animation 2.00 70.00 0.577 0.564      0.000603
## 6          audio:animation 2.00 70.00 1.352 0.265      0.001000
## 7 avatar:audio:animation 2.00 70.00 1.757 0.180      0.003000
```

ART Test

```
## Aligned Rank Transform of Factorial Model
```

```
##
```

```
## Call:
```

```
## art(formula = excitement ~ avatar * audio * animation + (1 |
##     v_ID), data = data_long)
```

```
##
```

```
## Column sums of aligned responses (should all be ~0):
```

```
##           avatar           audio           animation
##           0             0             0
##      avatar:audio  avatar:animation  audio:animation
##           0             0             0
## avatar:audio:animation
##           0
```

```
##
```

```
## F values of ANOVAs on aligned responses not of interest (should all be ~0):
```

```
##   Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
##     0         0         0         0         0         0
```

```
## Analysis of Variance of Aligned Rank Transformed Data
```

```
##
```

```
## Table Type: Analysis of Deviance Table (Type III Wald F tests with Kenward-Roger df)
```

```
## Model: Mixed Effects (lmer)
```

```
## Response: art(excitement)
```

```
##
```

```
##           F Df Df.res    Pr(>F)
## 1 avatar      4.4142  1    385  0.036290 *
## 2 audio       3.1626  1    385  0.076132 .
## 3 animation  14.1477  2    385 1.1777e-06 ***
## 4 avatar:audio  1.8578  1    385  0.173676
## 5 avatar:animation  4.1190  2    385  0.016982 *
## 6 audio:animation  1.3444  2    385  0.261906
## 7 avatar:audio:animation  2.4376  2    385  0.088717 .
```

```
## ---
```

```
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

ART.Con Avatar:Animation

```
## NOTE: Results may be misleading due to involvement in interactions
```

```
## contrast estimate SE df t.ratio p.value
## C,PC - C,PD  11.58 11.8 385  0.984  1.0000
## C,PC - C,PS  15.28 11.8 385  1.298  1.0000
## C,PC - R,PC -19.75 11.8 385 -1.678  1.0000
## C,PC - R,PD   1.18 11.8 385  0.100  1.0000
## C,PC - R,PS  14.04 11.8 385  1.193  1.0000
## C,PD - C,PS   3.69 11.8 385  0.314  1.0000
## C,PD - R,PC -31.33 11.8 385 -2.663  0.1212
## C,PD - R,PD -10.40 11.8 385 -0.884  1.0000
```

```

## C,PD - R,PS      2.46 11.8 385   0.209  1.0000
## C,PS - R,PC     -35.03 11.8 385  -2.977  0.0465
## C,PS - R,PD     -14.10 11.8 385  -1.198  1.0000
## C,PS - R,PS      -1.24 11.8 385  -0.105  1.0000
## R,PC - R,PD      20.93 11.8 385   1.779  1.0000
## R,PC - R,PS      33.79 11.8 385   2.872  0.0647
## R,PD - R,PS      12.86 11.8 385   1.093  1.0000
##
## Results are averaged over the levels of: audio
## Degrees-of-freedom method: kenward-roger
## P value adjustment: bonferroni method for 15 tests

```

ART.Con Animation

```

## NOTE: Results may be misleading due to involvement in interactions

## contrast estimate  SE  df t.ratio p.value
## PC - PD           34.31 8.27 385   4.150  0.0001
## PC - PS           40.98 8.27 385   4.957  <.0001
## PD - PS            6.67 8.27 385   0.807  1.0000
##
## Results are averaged over the levels of: avatar, audio
## Degrees-of-freedom method: kenward-roger
## P value adjustment: bonferroni method for 3 tests

```

Analysis Calmness

descriptive analysis

```
## # A tibble: 12 x 7
##   avatar audio animation variable      n mean  sd
##   <fct> <fct> <fct>   <fct>   <dbl> <dbl> <dbl>
## 1 C     MA     PC     calmness  36  3.83  1.63
## 2 C     MA     PD     calmness  36  3.81  1.67
## 3 C     MA     PS     calmness  36  3.81  1.70
## 4 C     SA     PC     calmness  36  3.97  1.70
## 5 C     SA     PD     calmness  36  3.89  1.74
## 6 C     SA     PS     calmness  36  3.92  1.83
## 7 R     MA     PC     calmness  36  4.19  1.79
## 8 R     MA     PD     calmness  36  4.03  1.73
## 9 R     MA     PS     calmness  36  3.89  1.67
## 10 R    SA     PC     calmness  36  3.81  1.65
## 11 R    SA     PD     calmness  36  3.92  1.66
## 12 R    SA     PS     calmness  36  3.94  1.64
```

mean and SD values grouped by avatar

```
## # A tibble: 2 x 4
##   avatar count mean  sd
##   <fct> <int> <dbl> <dbl>
## 1 C      216  3.87  1.69
## 2 R      216  3.96  1.68
```

Outliers

```
## [1] avatar          audio              animation          v_ID
## [5] OrderCondition    Condition          excitement         calmness
## [9] externalization   auvicoherence     auplausibility    distance
## [13] ABP1_BehP1        ABP2_AppP1        ABP3_BehAppMatch  ABP4_coherence
## [17] ABP5_BehExp       ABP6_predict      SP1                SP2
## [21] SP3               SP4               SP5                avgabp
## [25] avgsp             avgaudio          is.outlier        is.extreme
## <0 Zeilen> (oder row.names mit Länge 0)
```

Normality assumptions (Shapiro-Wilk test and QQ-plot)

```
## # A tibble: 12 x 6
##   avatar audio animation variable statistic      p
##   <fct> <fct> <fct>   <chr>   <dbl> <dbl>
## 1 C     MA     PC     calmness  0.946 0.0764
## 2 C     MA     PD     calmness  0.938 0.0433
## 3 C     MA     PS     calmness  0.944 0.0691
## 4 C     SA     PC     calmness  0.952 0.121
## 5 C     SA     PD     calmness  0.930 0.0250
## 6 C     SA     PS     calmness  0.925 0.0173
## 7 R     MA     PC     calmness  0.938 0.0430
## 8 R     MA     PD     calmness  0.949 0.0966
## 9 R     MA     PS     calmness  0.944 0.0700
## 10 R    SA     PC     calmness  0.949 0.0986
## 11 R    SA     PD     calmness  0.934 0.0328
## 12 R    SA     PS     calmness  0.941 0.0535
```


3-way repeated measure Anova

```
## ANOVA Table (type III tests)
##
##          Effect DFn DFd    F    p p<.05      ges
## 1          avatar     1  35 1.844 0.183  7.61e-04
## 2           audio     1  35 0.094 0.761  3.05e-05
## 3      animation     2  70 0.188 0.829  2.40e-04
## 4   avatar:audio     1  35 4.138 0.050  * 1.00e-03
## 5  avatar:animation   2  70 0.057 0.945  7.23e-05
## 6  audio:animation    2  70 0.733 0.484  6.43e-04
## 7 avatar:audio:animation 2  70 0.848 0.433  8.71e-04
```

ART Test

```
## Aligned Rank Transform of Factorial Model
##
## Call:
## art(formula = calmness ~ avatar * audio * animation + (1 | v_ID),
##      data = data_long)
##
## Column sums of aligned responses (should all be ~0):
##          avatar          audio          animation
##          0            0            0
##   avatar:audio  avatar:animation  audio:animation
##          0            0            0
## avatar:audio:animation
##          0
```

```

##
## F values of ANOVAs on aligned responses not of interest (should all be ~0):
##   Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
##     0      0      0      0      0      0

## Analysis of Variance of Aligned Rank Transformed Data
##
## Table Type: Analysis of Deviance Table (Type III Wald F tests with Kenward-Roger df)
## Model: Mixed Effects (lmer)
## Response: art(calmness)
##
##
##           F Df Df.res    Pr(>F)
## 1 avatar      4.2561  1   385 0.0397786 *
## 2 audio       2.7575  1   385 0.0976126 .
## 3 animation   1.7924  2   385 0.1679462
## 4 avatar:audio  8.3626  1   385 0.0040476 **
## 5 avatar:animation  2.9233  2   385 0.0549493 .
## 6 audio:animation  0.6867  2   385 0.5038512
## 7 avatar:audio:animation 1.8971  2   385 0.1514082
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

ART.Con Avatar:Audio

## NOTE: Results may be misleading due to involvement in interactions

## contrast      estimate    SE df t.ratio p.value
## C,MA - C,SA   -8.306  8.18 385  -1.016  1.0000
## C,MA - R,MA  -17.736  8.18 385  -2.169  0.1839
## C,MA - R,SA   -0.458  8.18 385  -0.056  1.0000
## C,SA - R,MA   -9.431  8.18 385  -1.154  1.0000
## C,SA - R,SA    7.847  8.18 385   0.960  1.0000
## R,MA - R,SA   17.278  8.18 385   2.113  0.2113
##
## Results are averaged over the levels of: animation
## Degrees-of-freedom method: kenward-roger
## P value adjustment: bonferroni method for 6 tests

```

Audio Related Questions

Boxplot Audio related questions 1-4

```
## Using avatar, audio, animation as id variables
```

```
## Warning in geom_signif(inherit.aes = FALSE, data = annotation_df, aes(xmin =  
## start, : Ignoring unknown aesthetics: xmin, xmax, annotations, and y_position
```


Analysis Audio Visual Coherence

descriptive analysis

```
## # A tibble: 12 x 7
##   avatar audio animation variable      n mean  sd
##   <fct> <fct> <fct>   <fct>   <dbl> <dbl> <dbl>
## 1 C     MA     PC     auvicoherence 36 3.94 1.77
## 2 C     MA     PD     auvicoherence 36 3.72 1.75
## 3 C     MA     PS     auvicoherence 36 4.11 1.56
## 4 C     SA     PC     auvicoherence 36 4.39 1.57
## 5 C     SA     PD     auvicoherence 36 4.08 1.89
## 6 C     SA     PS     auvicoherence 36 4.67 1.39
## 7 R     MA     PC     auvicoherence 36 4.06 1.82
## 8 R     MA     PD     auvicoherence 36 3.92 1.64
## 9 R     MA     PS     auvicoherence 36 4.33 1.45
## 10 R    SA     PC     auvicoherence 36 4     1.91
## 11 R    SA     PD     auvicoherence 36 3.94 1.64
## 12 R    SA     PS     auvicoherence 36 4.25 1.38
```

mean and SD values grouped by audio

```
## # A tibble: 2 x 4
##   audio count mean  sd
##   <fct> <int> <dbl> <dbl>
## 1 MA     216 4.01 1.66
## 2 SA     216 4.22 1.64
```

mean and SD values grouped by animation

```
## # A tibble: 3 x 4
##   animation count mean  sd
##   <fct>      <int> <dbl> <dbl>
## 1 PC          144 4.10 1.76
## 2 PD          144 3.92 1.72
## 3 PS          144 4.34 1.45
```

mean and SD values grouped by avatar:audio

```
## `summarise()` has grouped output by 'avatar'. You can override using the
## `.groups` argument.
```

```
## # A tibble: 4 x 5
## # Groups:   avatar [2]
##   avatar audio count mean  sd
##   <fct> <fct> <int> <dbl> <dbl>
## 1 C     MA     108 3.93 1.69
## 2 C     SA     108 4.38 1.63
## 3 R     MA     108 4.10 1.64
## 4 R     SA     108 4.06 1.65
```

Outliers

```
## # A tibble: 8 x 28
##   avatar audio animation v_ID OrderCondition Condition excitement calmness
##   <fct> <fct> <fct>   <chr>      <int> <chr>          <int> <int>
## 1 C     SA     PC     p8          10 C_SA_PC         3      3
## 2 C     SA     PC     p10         6 C_SA_PC         1      4
## 3 C     SA     PC     p11         4 C_SA_PC         4      3
```

```

## 4 C      SA   PC      p23          4 C_SA_PC          2      2
## 5 C      SA   PC      p25          1 C_SA_PC          4      3
## 6 R      MA   PS      p10          3 R_MA_PS          1      4
## 7 R      MA   PS      P19          4 R_MA_PS          7      5
## 8 R      MA   PS      p24          7 R_MA_PS          1      7
## # i 20 more variables: externalization <int>, auvicoherence <int>,
## #   auplausibility <int>, distance <int>, ABP1_BehP1 <int>, ABP2_AppP1 <int>,
## #   ABP3_BehAppMatch <int>, ABP4_coherence <int>, ABP5_BehExp <int>,
## #   ABP6_predict <dbl>, SP1 <dbl>, SP2 <dbl>, SP3 <dbl>, SP4 <dbl>, SP5 <dbl>,
## #   avgabp <dbl>, avgsp <dbl>, avgaudio <dbl>, is.outlier <lgl>,
## #   is.extreme <lgl>

```

Normality assumptions (Shapiro-Wilk test and QQ-plot)

```

## # A tibble: 12 x 6
##   avatar audio animation variable      statistic      p
##   <fct> <fct> <fct>   <chr>          <dbl>    <dbl>
## 1 C      MA   PC      auvicoherence  0.936 0.0375
## 2 C      MA   PD      auvicoherence  0.933 0.0305
## 3 C      MA   PS      auvicoherence  0.896 0.00261
## 4 C      SA   PC      auvicoherence  0.941 0.0554
## 5 C      SA   PD      auvicoherence  0.896 0.00263
## 6 C      SA   PS      auvicoherence  0.821 0.0000434
## 7 R      MA   PC      auvicoherence  0.935 0.0347
## 8 R      MA   PD      auvicoherence  0.954 0.138
## 9 R      MA   PS      auvicoherence  0.945 0.0737
## 10 R     SA   PC      auvicoherence  0.903 0.00408
## 11 R     SA   PD      auvicoherence  0.929 0.0241
## 12 R     SA   PS      auvicoherence  0.951 0.109

```


3-way repeated measure Anova

```
## ANOVA Table (type III tests)
##
##           Effect DFn DFd      F      p p<.05      ges
## 1           avatar     1  35 0.477 0.494 4.51e-04
## 2            audio     1  35 2.747 0.106 4.00e-03
## 3       animation     2  70 3.564 0.034 * 1.10e-02
## 4   avatar:audio     1  35 4.957 0.033 * 6.00e-03
## 5  avatar:animation  2  70 0.279 0.757 4.69e-04
## 6  audio:animation  2  70 0.015 0.985 3.61e-05
## 7 avatar:audio:animation 2  70 0.212 0.809 3.65e-04
```

ART Test

```
## Aligned Rank Transform of Factorial Model
##
## Call:
## art(formula = auvicoherence ~ avatar * audio * animation + (1 |
##       v_ID), data = data_long)
##
## Column sums of aligned responses (should all be ~0):
##           avatar           audio           animation
##           0             0             0
##   avatar:audio  avatar:animation  audio:animation
##           0             0             0
## avatar:audio:animation
##           0
```

```

##
## F values of ANOVAs on aligned responses not of interest (should all be ~0):
##   Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
##     0      0      0      0      0      0

## Analysis of Variance of Aligned Rank Transformed Data
##
## Table Type: Analysis of Deviance Table (Type III Wald F tests with Kenward-Roger df)
## Model: Mixed Effects (lmer)
## Response: art(auvicoherence)
##
##
##           F Df Df.res    Pr(>F) eta.sq.part
## 1 avatar      0.89880  1    385 0.3436971  0.00232912
## 2 audio       5.30259  1    385 0.0218263  0.01358584 *
## 3 animation   6.22375  2    385 0.0021869  0.03131861 **
## 4 avatar:audio 4.70078  1    385 0.0307609  0.01206254 *
## 5 avatar:animation 0.67594  2    385 0.5092794  0.00349910
## 6 audio:animation 0.16187  2    385 0.8506133  0.00084015
## 7 avatar:audio:animation 0.57103  2    385 0.5654192  0.00295763
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

ART.Con avatar:audio

## NOTE: Results may be misleading due to involvement in interactions

## contrast estimate SE df t.ratio p.value
## C,MA - C,SA -32.27 11.9 385 -2.713 0.0418
## C,MA - R,MA -8.38 11.9 385 -0.704 1.0000
## C,MA - R,SA -12.96 11.9 385 -1.090 1.0000
## C,SA - R,MA 23.90 11.9 385 2.009 0.2715
## C,SA - R,SA 19.31 11.9 385 1.623 0.6322
## R,MA - R,SA -4.59 11.9 385 -0.386 1.0000
##
## Results are averaged over the levels of: animation
## Degrees-of-freedom method: kenward-roger
## P value adjustment: bonferroni method for 6 tests

ART.Con audio

## NOTE: Results may be misleading due to involvement in interactions

## contrast estimate SE df t.ratio p.value
## MA - SA -19.4 8.44 385 -2.303 0.0218
##
## Results are averaged over the levels of: avatar, animation
## Degrees-of-freedom method: kenward-roger

ART.Con animation

## NOTE: Results may be misleading due to involvement in interactions

## contrast estimate SE df t.ratio p.value
## PC - PD 20.3 10.3 385 1.971 0.1482
## PC - PS -15.9 10.3 385 -1.548 0.3672
## PD - PS -36.2 10.3 385 -3.520 0.0015
##
## Results are averaged over the levels of: avatar, audio
## Degrees-of-freedom method: kenward-roger

```

```
## P value adjustment: bonferroni method for 3 tests
```

Analysis Audio Plausibility

descriptive analysis

```
## # A tibble: 12 x 7
##   avatar audio animation variable      n mean  sd
##   <fct> <fct> <fct>   <fct>   <dbl> <dbl> <dbl>
## 1 C     MA     PC     auplausibility 36 4.22 1.55
## 2 C     MA     PD     auplausibility 36 3.92 1.52
## 3 C     MA     PS     auplausibility 36 4.08 1.44
## 4 C     SA     PC     auplausibility 36 4.58 1.30
## 5 C     SA     PD     auplausibility 36 4.19 1.49
## 6 C     SA     PS     auplausibility 36 4.33 1.59
## 7 R     MA     PC     auplausibility 36 4.22 1.62
## 8 R     MA     PD     auplausibility 36 3.94 1.62
## 9 R     MA     PS     auplausibility 36 4.19 1.53
## 10 R    SA     PC     auplausibility 36 4.11 1.74
## 11 R    SA     PD     auplausibility 36 4     1.57
## 12 R    SA     PS     auplausibility 36 4.25 1.61
```

mean and SD values grouped by audio

```
## # A tibble: 2 x 4
##   audio count mean  sd
##   <fct> <int> <dbl> <dbl>
## 1 MA     216  4.10  1.54
## 2 SA     216  4.25  1.55
```

Outliers

```
## # A tibble: 7 x 28
##   avatar audio animation v_ID OrderCondition Condition excitement calmness
##   <fct> <fct> <fct>   <chr>      <int> <chr>          <int>   <int>
## 1 C     SA     PC     p15         5 C_SA_PC         4       6
## 2 C     SA     PC     P36         2 C_SA_PC         3       2
## 3 C     SA     PD     p8          12 C_SA_PD         3       3
## 4 C     SA     PD     p24         4 C_SA_PD         7       7
## 5 C     SA     PD     p25         2 C_SA_PD         4       2
## 6 C     SA     PS     p10         12 C_SA_PS         1       4
## 7 C     SA     PS     p25         6 C_SA_PS         6       6
## # i 20 more variables: externalization <int>, auvicoherence <int>,
## #   auplausibility <int>, distance <int>, ABP1_BehP1 <int>, ABP2_AppP1 <int>,
## #   ABP3_BehAppMatch <int>, ABP4_coherence <int>, ABP5_BehExp <int>,
## #   ABP6_predict <dbl>, SP1 <dbl>, SP2 <dbl>, SP3 <dbl>, SP4 <dbl>, SP5 <dbl>,
## #   avgabp <dbl>, avgsp <dbl>, avgaudio <dbl>, is.outlier <lgl>,
## #   is.extreme <lgl>
```

Normality assumptions (Shapiro-Wilk test and QQ-plot)

```
## # A tibble: 12 x 6
##   avatar audio animation variable      statistic      p
##   <fct> <fct> <fct>   <chr>         <dbl> <dbl>
## 1 C     MA     PC     auplausibility 0.933 0.0311
## 2 C     MA     PD     auplausibility 0.920 0.0122
## 3 C     MA     PS     auplausibility 0.952 0.119
## 4 C     SA     PC     auplausibility 0.940 0.0513
## 5 C     SA     PD     auplausibility 0.933 0.0305
## 6 C     SA     PS     auplausibility 0.947 0.0832
```

```

## 7 R      MA    PC      auplausibility  0.953 0.131
## 8 R      MA    PD      auplausibility  0.930 0.0256
## 9 R      MA    PS      auplausibility  0.934 0.0320
## 10 R     SA    PC      auplausibility  0.939 0.0486
## 11 R     SA    PD      auplausibility  0.941 0.0549
## 12 R     SA    PS      auplausibility  0.919 0.0116

```


3-way repeated measure Anova

```

## ANOVA Table (type III tests)
##
##          Effect DFn DFd    F    p p<.05      ges
## 1          avatar   1  35 1.163 0.288 1.00e-03
## 2           audio   1  35 1.724 0.198 2.00e-03
## 3        animation   2  70 1.912 0.155 6.00e-03
## 4   avatar:audio   1  35 2.067 0.159 2.00e-03
## 5  avatar:animation  2  70 0.672 0.514 1.00e-03
## 6   audio:animation  2  70 0.022 0.978 3.21e-05
## 7 avatar:audio:animation  2  70 0.212 0.810 4.17e-04

```

ART Test

```

## Aligned Rank Transform of Factorial Model
##
## Call:
## art(formula = auplausibility ~ avatar * audio * animation + (1 |
##       v_ID), data = data_long)
##

```

```

## Column sums of aligned responses (should all be ~0):
##          avatar          audio          animation
##          0            0            0
##   avatar:audio  avatar:animation  audio:animation
##          0            0            0
## avatar:audio:animation
##          0
##
## F values of ANOVAs on aligned responses not of interest (should all be ~0):
##   Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
##     0      0      0      0      0      0

## Analysis of Variance of Aligned Rank Transformed Data
##
## Table Type: Analysis of Deviance Table (Type III Wald F tests with Kenward-Roger df)
## Model: Mixed Effects (lmer)
## Response: art(auplausibility)
##
##              F Df Df.res  Pr(>F) eta.sq.part
## 1 avatar          1.14959  1    385 0.284307  0.0029770
## 2 audio           4.02665  1    385 0.045486  0.0103506 *
## 3 animation       2.79865  2    385 0.062131  0.0143301 .
## 4 avatar:audio    3.03533  1    385 0.082268  0.0078223 .
## 5 avatar:animation 1.31849  2    385 0.268744  0.0068027
## 6 audio:animation 0.85019  2    385 0.428133  0.0043972
## 7 avatar:audio:animation 0.36162  2    385 0.696782  0.0018750
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

ART.Con audio

## NOTE: Results may be misleading due to involvement in interactions

## contrast estimate  SE  df t.ratio p.value
## MA - SA          -16.2 8.09 385  -2.007  0.0455
##
## Results are averaged over the levels of: avatar, animation
## Degrees-of-freedom method: kenward-roger

```

Appearance and Behavior Plausibility

Boxplot appearance and behavior plausibility shows mean values of related questions 1-6

```
## Using avatar, audio, animation as id variables
```

```
## Warning in geom_signif(inherit.aes = FALSE, data = annotation_df, aes(xmin =  
## start, : Ignoring unknown aesthetics: xmin, xmax, annotations, and y_position
```

```
## Warning: Removed 7 rows containing non-finite values (`stat_boxplot()`).
```

```
## Removed 7 rows containing non-finite values (`stat_boxplot()`).
```


Analysis Appearance Behavior Mean

descriptive analysis

```
## # A tibble: 12 x 7
##   avatar audio animation variable      n mean  sd
##   <fct> <fct> <fct>    <fct>    <dbl> <dbl> <dbl>
## 1 C     MA     PC     avgabp     36  3.61  1.34
## 2 C     MA     PD     avgabp     36  3.52  1.32
## 3 C     MA     PS     avgabp     36  3.72  1.30
## 4 C     SA     PC     avgabp     36  3.74  1.37
## 5 C     SA     PD     avgabp     36  3.52  1.20
## 6 C     SA     PS     avgabp     36  3.75  1.27
## 7 R     MA     PC     avgabp     36  3.99  1.23
## 8 R     MA     PD     avgabp     36  3.69  1.35
## 9 R     MA     PS     avgabp     36  3.91  1.26
## 10 R    SA     PC     avgabp     36  3.71  1.24
## 11 R    SA     PD     avgabp     36  3.81  1.23
## 12 R    SA     PS     avgabp     36  3.91  1.25
```

mean and SD values grouped by animation

```
## # A tibble: 3 x 4
##   animation count mean  sd
##   <fct>    <int> <dbl> <dbl>
## 1 PC         144  3.76  1.29
## 2 PD         144  3.64  1.27
## 3 PS         144  3.82  1.26
```

mean and SD values grouped by avatar

```
## # A tibble: 2 x 4
##   avatar count mean  sd
##   <fct> <int> <dbl> <dbl>
## 1 C     216  3.64  1.29
## 2 R     216  3.84  1.25
```

Outliers

```
## # A tibble: 11 x 7
##   avatar audio animation avgabp v_ID is.outlier is.extreme
##   <fct> <fct> <fct>    <dbl> <chr> <lgl>    <lgl>
## 1 C     MA     PS     0.667 p11  TRUE     FALSE
## 2 R     MA     PC     1      p8    TRUE     FALSE
## 3 R     MA     PD     0.333 p11  TRUE     FALSE
## 4 R     MA     PS     1.33  p8    TRUE     FALSE
## 5 R     MA     PS     1.17  p11  TRUE     FALSE
## 6 R     MA     PS     1.33  P20  TRUE     FALSE
## 7 R     MA     PS     1.5   P6    TRUE     FALSE
## 8 R     SA     PD     0.833 p8    TRUE     FALSE
## 9 R     SA     PD     1.5   p10  TRUE     FALSE
## 10 R    SA     PD     0.5   p11  TRUE     FALSE
## 11 R    SA     PD     1.5   P6    TRUE     FALSE
```

Normality assumptions (Shapiro-Wilk test and QQ-plot)

```
## # A tibble: 12 x 6
##   avatar audio animation variable statistic      p
##   <fct> <fct> <fct>    <chr>    <dbl>    <dbl>
```

##	1	C	MA	PC	avgabp	0.948	0.0913
##	2	C	MA	PD	avgabp	0.942	0.0581
##	3	C	MA	PS	avgabp	0.933	0.0307
##	4	C	SA	PC	avgabp	0.943	0.0615
##	5	C	SA	PD	avgabp	0.950	0.105
##	6	C	SA	PS	avgabp	0.954	0.138
##	7	R	MA	PC	avgabp	0.968	0.378
##	8	R	MA	PD	avgabp	0.946	0.0797
##	9	R	MA	PS	avgabp	0.922	0.0139
##	10	R	SA	PC	avgabp	0.969	0.401
##	11	R	SA	PD	avgabp	0.913	0.00786
##	12	R	SA	PS	avgabp	0.949	0.0996

3-way repeated measure Anova

ANOVA Table (type III tests)

##	Effect	DFn	DFd	F	p	p<.05	ges
## 1	avatar	1.00	35.00	5.354e+00	0.027	*	6.00e-03
## 2	audio	1.00	35.00	5.590e-30	1.000		3.43e-33
## 3	animation	1.66	57.93	9.250e-01	0.386		4.00e-03
## 4	avatar:audio	1.00	35.00	1.225e+00	0.276		4.31e-04
## 5	avatar:animation	2.00	70.00	8.000e-02	0.923		9.03e-05
## 6	audio:animation	2.00	70.00	4.660e-01	0.629		4.86e-04
## 7	avatar:audio:animation	2.00	70.00	2.070e+00	0.134		2.00e-03

ART Test

```

## Aligned Rank Transform of Factorial Model
##
## Call:
## art(formula = avgabp ~ avatar * audio * animation + (1 | v_ID),
##      data = data_B)
##
## Column sums of aligned responses (should all be ~0):
##           avatar           audio           animation
##           0             0             0
##      avatar:audio  avatar:animation  audio:animation
##           0             0             0
## avatar:audio:animation
##           0
##
## F values of ANOVAs on aligned responses not of interest (should all be ~0):
##      Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
##           0         0         0         0         0         0
##
## Analysis of Variance of Aligned Rank Transformed Data
##
## Table Type: Analysis of Deviance Table (Type III Wald F tests with Kenward-Roger df)
## Model: Mixed Effects (lmer)
## Response: art(avgabp)
##
##           F Df Df.res  Pr(>F)
## 1 avatar      5.2724e+00  1    385 0.022203 *
## 2 audio      3.9788e-07  1    385 0.999497
## 3 animation  1.9153e+00  2    385 0.148692
## 4 avatar:audio  6.4457e-01  1    385 0.422555
## 5 avatar:animation  1.1071e-01  2    385 0.895224
## 6 audio:animation  6.8216e-02  2    385 0.934070
## 7 avatar:audio:animation  1.2251e+00  2    385 0.294879
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
ART.Con Animation
## NOTE: Results may be misleading due to involvement in interactions
## contrast estimate SE df t.ratio p.value
## PC - PD      9.43 8.97 385  1.051 0.8820
## PC - PS     -8.12 8.97 385 -0.905 1.0000
## PD - PS    -17.55 8.97 385 -1.955 0.1538
##
## Results are averaged over the levels of: avatar, audio
## Degrees-of-freedom method: kenward-roger
## P value adjustment: bonferroni method for 3 tests

```

Social Presence

Boxplot social presence shows mean values of related questions 1-5

```
## Using avatar, audio, animation as id variables
```

```
## Warning in geom_signif(inherit.aes = FALSE, data = annotation_df, aes(xmin =  
## start, : Ignoring unknown aesthetics: xmin, xmax, annotations, and y_position
```


Analysis Social Presence Mean

descriptive analysis

```
## # A tibble: 12 x 7
##   avatar audio animation variable      n mean  sd
##   <fct> <fct> <fct> <fct> <dbl> <dbl> <dbl>
## 1 C     MA     PC     avgsp    36 0.372 0.753
## 2 C     MA     PD     avgsp    36 0.183 0.934
## 3 C     MA     PS     avgsp    36 0.289 1
## 4 C     SA     PC     avgsp    36 0.311 0.848
## 5 C     SA     PD     avgsp    36 0.056 0.936
## 6 C     SA     PS     avgsp    36 0.261 0.822
## 7 R     MA     PC     avgsp    36 0.361 0.775
## 8 R     MA     PD     avgsp    36 0.067 0.96
## 9 R     MA     PS     avgsp    36 0.2   0.885
## 10 R    SA     PC     avgsp    36 0.139 0.96
## 11 R    SA     PD     avgsp    36 0.133 0.887
## 12 R    SA     PS     avgsp    36 0.35  0.913
```

mean and SD values grouped by animation

```
## # A tibble: 3 x 4
##   animation count mean  sd
##   <fct>      <int> <dbl> <dbl>
## 1 PC           144 0.296 0.834
## 2 PD           144 0.110 0.921
## 3 PS           144 0.275 0.899
```

Outliers

```
## # A tibble: 4 x 7
##   avatar audio animation avgsp v_ID is.outlier is.extreme
##   <fct> <fct> <fct> <dbl> <chr> <lgl> <lgl>
## 1 R     MA     PD     -2.8 p11 TRUE     FALSE
## 2 R     SA     PC     -2.6 p11 TRUE     FALSE
## 3 R     SA     PD     -2.8 p11 TRUE     TRUE
## 4 R     SA     PS     -2.6 p11 TRUE     FALSE
```

Normality assumptions (Shapiro-Wilk test and QQ-plot)

```
## # A tibble: 12 x 6
##   avatar audio animation variable statistic      p
##   <fct> <fct> <fct> <chr> <dbl> <dbl>
## 1 C     MA     PC     avgsp    0.945 0.0731
## 2 C     MA     PD     avgsp    0.950 0.103
## 3 C     MA     PS     avgsp    0.969 0.388
## 4 C     SA     PC     avgsp    0.952 0.120
## 5 C     SA     PD     avgsp    0.950 0.105
## 6 C     SA     PS     avgsp    0.981 0.787
## 7 R     MA     PC     avgsp    0.987 0.944
## 8 R     MA     PD     avgsp    0.965 0.304
## 9 R     MA     PS     avgsp    0.975 0.593
## 10 R    SA     PC     avgsp    0.971 0.459
## 11 R    SA     PD     avgsp    0.935 0.0346
## 12 R    SA     PS     avgsp    0.950 0.105
```


3-way repeated measure Anova

```
## ANOVA Table (type III tests)
##
##           Effect DFn  DFd    F    p p<.05    ges
## 1           avatar 1.00 35.00 0.358 0.553    0.000443
## 2            audio 1.00 35.00 0.490 0.489    0.000443
## 3      animation 1.54 53.86 4.473 0.024    * 0.009000
## 4   avatar:audio 1.00 35.00 0.504 0.482    0.000400
## 5 avatar:animation 2.00 70.00 0.398 0.673    0.000502
## 6   audio:animation 2.00 70.00 2.255 0.112    0.002000
## 7 avatar:audio:animation 2.00 70.00 1.306 0.277    0.002000
```

ART Test

```
## Aligned Rank Transform of Factorial Model
##
## Call:
## art(formula = avgsp ~ avatar * audio * animation + (1 | v_ID),
##      data = data_SP)
##
## Column sums of aligned responses (should all be ~0):
##           avatar           audio           animation
##           0             0             0
##   avatar:audio  avatar:animation  audio:animation
##           0             0             0
## avatar:audio:animation
##           0
```

```

##
## F values of ANOVAs on aligned responses not of interest (should all be ~0):
##   Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
##     0      0      0      0      0      0

## Analysis of Variance of Aligned Rank Transformed Data
##
## Table Type: Analysis of Deviance Table (Type III Wald F tests with Kenward-Roger df)
## Model: Mixed Effects (lmer)
## Response: art(avgsp)
##
##              F Df Df.res  Pr(>F)
## 1 avatar          0.45895  1    385 0.498523
## 2 audio           0.25724  1    385 0.612314
## 3 animation       4.15512  2    385 0.016393 *
## 4 avatar:audio    0.56053  1    385 0.454506
## 5 avatar:animation 0.33329  2    385 0.716772
## 6 audio:animation 0.88595  2    385 0.413163
## 7 avatar:audio:animation 0.47093  2    385 0.624778
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

ART.Con Animation

## NOTE: Results may be misleading due to involvement in interactions

## contrast estimate  SE  df t.ratio p.value
## PC - PD      21.632 8.59 385   2.518 0.0367
## PC - PS       0.368 8.59 385   0.043 1.0000
## PD - PS     -21.264 8.59 385  -2.475 0.0413
##
## Results are averaged over the levels of: avatar, audio
## Degrees-of-freedom method: kenward-roger
## P value adjustment: bonferroni method for 3 tests

```